

A MESOSCALE MODEL FOR THE PREDICTION OF COMPOSITES MATERIALS UNTIL FINAL FAILURE

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SUMMARY

The degradation and failure prediction of composites materials is a real industrial challenge. Recent advances enable to fully understand the failure mechanisms of these materials. An enhanced version of the damage mesomodel for laminates is presented. This model coupled with a high performance resolution strategy enables us to simulate, until final failure, the degradation of industrial pieces.

Keywords: Composites Materials, Damage, Failure, Microcracking, Delamination.

INTRODUCTION

One of the main challenges in the design of composites consists in calculating, at any point and at any time until final failure, the damage state of a composite structure subjected to complex loading. Damage is a complex degradation phenomenon involving both the layer (progressive transverse microcracking, brittle fracture of the fibers, debonding of the fibers-matrix interface) and the interlaminar bonds (delamination).

In order to take all these phenomena into account, a damage mesomodel for laminated composites was proposed in [1]. In our work, we used an enhanced version of this damage mesomodel [2]. In this approach, the laminate is described as stacking sequence of two homogeneous mesoconstituents: the elementary layer and the interface (Figure 1). Mesodamage indicators quantify the damage state of each mesoconstituents, which can be connected directly to the loss of stiffness. An important point is that the damage state is assumed to be uniform throughout the thickness of the elementary layer, but not throughout the whole thickness of the laminate. This assumption makes the model nonlocal on the scale of the elementary layer. The interface, which is a two-dimensional entity, performs the transfer of stresses and displacement from one ply to another. Recent works showed that the mechanical behaviour of an interface depends on the relative orientation and internal variables of the two adjacent layers. This nonlocal behaviour is also necessary for the correct simulation of delamination.

THE DEGRADATION MECHANISMS

The main mechanisms involved in the degradation of a laminate are the following:

- Diffuse intralaminar degradation: This mechanism is associated with degradation on a very small scale (the scale of the fiber), such as fiber-matrix splitting or matrix rupture between the fibers [3-6]; locally, *i.e.* on the scale of the elementary layer, this degradation is assumed to be homogeneous.
- Inelastic deformation: this phenomenon is due mainly to friction between the splitting interfaces and to plasticity of the matrix. In this case, there is no plastic flow in the direction of the fibers: $\dot{\epsilon}_1^p = 0$. (The subscript 1 denotes the direction of the fibers.)
- Transverse microcracking: this mechanism corresponds to the percolation of diffuse damage into cracks, which are parallel to the fibers and extend fully across the elementary layer. Many studies of this phenomenon can be found in the literature on the micromechanics of stratified materials [8-9].
- Diffuse interface degradation: transverse microcracks extend throughout the thickness of the elementary layer and are stopped by the interlaminar interface. This results in high-stress zones at the crack tips leading to local degradation of the interlaminar interface, which can be easily observed on the elementary layer's scale [7].
- Fiber breakage: this is the last phenomenon, occurring either in traction or in compression, before the final failure of the specimen.

In most practical cases, damage is initiated by the diffuse mechanisms. Then, the accumulation of fiber-matrix debonding phenomena followed by their coalescence leads to transverse microcracking and local delamination. The competition between transverse microcracking and local delamination ends with the saturation of transverse microcracking and is relayed by the catastrophic development of local delamination; Finally, local delamination can lead to macroscopic interlaminar debonding due to the coalescence of fibers-matrix debonding under out-of-plane macroloading (e.g. close to geometric accidents such as holes). Fiber breakage occurs in the final stage of the degradation process, and usually results in a dramatic drop of the macroscopic stiffness.

THE DAMAGE MESOMODEL FOR LAMINATES

The damage mesomodel for laminates describes the behaviour of a laminate on the mesoscale through two mesoconstituents, which are continuous media: The elementary layer and the interface (Figure 1).

Figure 1 The model of a laminate.

Such a mesomodel is based on two assumptions. The first assumption is that the behaviour of any laminated structure can be reconstructed from the two elementary mesoconstituents. The second assumption is that the damage state is uniform throughout the thickness of the elementary layer (but not throughout the thickness of the laminated composite). In the early version of the model, the behaviour law of each mesoconstituents was considered to be intrinsic. Recent works, however, showed that on the mesoscale the evolution law of an interface is coupled with the internal variables of the adjacent layers.

The Elementary Layer

The elementary layer is defined by the classical energy for

$$2e_d = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_3 \end{bmatrix}^t [S] \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_3 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{G_{12}^0(1-\bar{d}_{12})(1-d)} + \frac{\sigma_{13}^2}{G_{13}^0(1-d)} + \frac{\sigma_{23}^2}{G_{23}^0(1-\bar{d}_{23})(1-d_{23})}$$

where

$$[S] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1^0(1-d_f)} & -\frac{\nu_{12}^0}{E_1^0} & -\frac{\nu_{13}^0}{E_1^0} \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}^0}{E_1^0} & \frac{1}{E_2^0(1-[\sigma_2]^+ \bar{d}_{22})(1-[\sigma_2]^+ d')} & -\frac{\nu_{23}^0}{E_2^0(1-[\sigma_2]^+ \bar{d}_{22})} \\ -\frac{\nu_{13}^0}{E_1^0} & -\frac{\nu_{23}^0}{E_2^0(1-[\sigma_2]^+ \bar{d}_{22})} & \frac{1}{E_2^0(1-[\sigma_3]^+ d')} \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$(1-d_{23}) = \frac{1-d'}{1 - \frac{\nu_{23}^0}{1+\nu_{23}^0} d'}$$

E_i^0 , G_{ij}^0 and ν_{ij}^0 designate the undamaged elastic parameter, σ_{ij} the stress and S the compliance operator. The energy equation is written in a local reference frame defined by the fiber's direction (N_1) the in-plane and out-of-plane transverse direction (N_2, N_3). In the case of carbon fiber composite a non-linear elastic behavior in the fiber's direction is observed. This phenomenon is introduced by a modification of the undamaged Young modulus in the fiber direction E_1^0

$$E_1^0 = E_1^0(\varepsilon_1) = E_{INI} \left(1 + \langle \varepsilon_1 \rangle_+ E^+ + \langle \varepsilon_1 \rangle_- E^- \right)$$

where E_{INI} is the Young modulus in the fiber direction at the origin, and E^+ and E^- are material parameters.

In the previous equations $[\cdot]^+$ denotes the Heaviside function and $\langle \varepsilon_1 \rangle_+$ $\langle \varepsilon_1 \rangle_-$ the positive and negative part of the strain in the fiber direction.

Consequently, if $\sigma_2 < 0$, the microcracks are closed and no observable damage occurs.

The damage indicators, which are constant throughout the thickness, are associated with the following degradation mechanisms:

- fiber breakage: d_f ,
- diffuse intralaminar degradation: d' , d , d_{23} ,
- transverse microcracking: \bar{d}_{22} , \bar{d}_{12} , \bar{d}_{23} .

The Elementary Layer: Damage Forces and Evolution Laws

The damage evolution laws use classical thermodynamic forces

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{Y}_{d_f} &= \left\langle \left\langle -\frac{\partial e_d}{\partial d_f} \right\rangle \right\rangle_H \\ \bar{Y}_d &= \left\langle \left\langle -\frac{\partial e_d}{\partial d} \right\rangle \right\rangle_H & \bar{Y}_{d'} &= \left\langle \left\langle -\frac{\partial e_d}{\partial d'} \right\rangle \right\rangle_H \\ \bar{Y}_{\bar{d}_{22}} &= \left\langle \left\langle -H \frac{\partial e_d}{\partial \bar{d}_{22}} \right\rangle \right\rangle_H & \bar{Y}_{\bar{d}_{12}} &= \left\langle \left\langle -H \frac{\partial e_d}{\partial \bar{d}_{12}} \right\rangle \right\rangle_H & \bar{Y}_{\bar{d}_{23}} &= \left\langle \left\langle -H \frac{\partial e_d}{\partial \bar{d}_{23}} \right\rangle \right\rangle_H\end{aligned}$$

where the H is the thickness of the elementary layer and $\langle \langle \cdot \rangle \rangle_H$ denotes the mean value throughout the thickness of the elementary layer. This operator is very important because it ensures that the damage indicator remains constant throughout the thickness of the elementary layer. This operator makes the model nonlocal on the scale of the elementary layer.

Then, the damage evolution laws are given by:

$$\begin{aligned}d_f &= f_f(\bar{Y}_{d_f}, \bar{Y}_{d'}) & \text{if } d_f < 1, & \quad d_f = 1 \text{ otherwise} \\ d &= f_d(\sqrt{\bar{Y}_d + b_y \bar{Y}_{d'}}) & \text{if } d < 1, & \quad d = 1 \text{ otherwise} \\ d' &= bd & \text{if } d' < 1, & \quad d' = 1 \text{ otherwise}\end{aligned}$$

where b and b_y are coupling parameter. Functions f_f and f_d depend on the material, progressive as well as brittle evolution can be modeled. The function f_f depends also of $\bar{Y}_{d'}$ to take into account the compression-shearing coupling in fibers direction.

For a complete description of these functions, see [1]. Diffuse damage is accompanied by irreversible inelastic behavior due to friction of the splitting interfaces and plasticity of the matrix. A classical plastic model is used to model the inelastic behavior.

The case of transverse microcracking is different and is taken into account by using an equivalent microcracking rate ρ for the elementary layer [1].

$$\rho = f_\rho(\bar{Y}_{\bar{d}_{22}}, \bar{Y}_{\bar{d}_{12}}, \bar{Y}_{\bar{d}_{23}})$$

The micro-meso relations developed previously in [10] enable one to homogenize this mechanism in order to define three damage indicators and the associated evolution laws:

$$\bar{d}_{22} = f_{22}(\rho)$$

$$\bar{d}_{12} = f_{12}(\rho)$$

$$\bar{d}_{23} = f_{23}(\rho)$$

Remarks:

These damage indicators are not independent of one another because they are all related to the microcracking rate ρ through the layer homogenization problem [10].

The damage indicators do not systematically range between 0 and 1, but are limited by the positive definiteness of the stiffness operator, when this condition is no longer fulfilled we consider that the material is completely degraded.

The Interface

The interface, which is introduced in order to model the debonding of two adjacent layers, can be viewed as a small thickness of matrix between two elementary layers. This is a two-dimensional entity, which ensures the transfer of stresses and displacement from one elementary layer to another.

$$[[U]] = U^+ - U^- = [[U_1]]N_1 + [[U_2]]N_2 + [[U_3]]N_3$$

where $[[U]]$ denotes the displacement jump between the upper and lower surface of the interface. A local reference frame of orthotropic direction 1, 2 and 3 is associated with the interface: 3 is normal to the interface, 1 and 2 are the bisectors of the angles (θ) formed by the fibers of the upper and lower elementary layers (Figure 2)

Figure 2 Orthotropic direction of the interface.

We use the same formalism to define the elastic strain energy of the interface:

$$2e_d = \frac{\sigma_3^2}{K_3^0(1 - [\sigma_3]^+ d_I)} + \frac{\sigma_{13}^2}{K_1^0(1 - d_{II})} + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{K_2^0(1 - d_{III})}$$

where K_1^0 , K_2^0 and K_3^0 are the elastic stiffness coefficients of the undamaged interface, and d_I , d_{II} and d_{III} the three damage indicator, which can vary between 0 and 1. The Heaviside function $[]^+$ is introduced in order to take into account the unilateral behavior of the interface in mode I. In [1], the interface's elastic coefficient were shown to be of the order of E_m/h , where E_m is the Young's modulus and h the thickness of the thin layer of matrix.

The Interface: Damage Forces And Evolution Laws

Classically, the thermodynamic forces associated with the damage indicators are:

$$Y_I = -\frac{\partial e_d}{\partial d_I}, Y_{II} = -\frac{\partial e_d}{\partial d_{II}}, Y_{III} = -\frac{\partial e_d}{\partial d_{III}}$$

The damage evolution laws used in this study are based on the assumption that the evolutions of the various damage indicators are highly coupled and governed by a unique "equivalent" damage force \bar{Y} .

$$\bar{Y}_t = \sup_{\tau \leq t} \left((Y_I)^\alpha + (\gamma_{II} Y_{II})^\alpha + (\gamma_{III} Y_{III})^\alpha \right)^{1/\alpha}$$

where α is a material constant, and γ_{II} and γ_{III} coupling constants.

Then, in statics, a damage evolution law is defined by the choice of a material function w :

$$w = \left(\frac{n}{1+n} \frac{\langle \bar{Y}_t - Y_0 \rangle_+}{Y_c - Y_0} \right)^n$$

where n , Y_0 and Y_c are material parameters. In the current version of the mesomodel, the damage evolution laws of the interface are highly coupled with the state variables of the adjacent layers [10]. This coupling is achieved through the mean value ρ of the microcracking rates of the upper and lower adjacent layers.

$$\rho = \frac{\rho^+ + \rho^-}{2}$$

$$d_I = w$$

$$d_{II} = w + (1 - d_I) \mathfrak{P} a_i \rho \sin^2(\theta)$$

$$d_{III} = w + (1 - d_I) \mathfrak{P} a_i \rho \cos^2(\theta)$$

where a_i is a coupling constant obtained numerically from the microproblem [1].

The mean-value operator used in the evolution law of the layer and the coupled interface evolution law make the model highly nonlocal. Special care must be taken to ensure the correct implementation and integration of the evolution laws [2].

Implementation

In the previous section, we derived a model, which follows the formalism of damage mechanics on the mesoscale. This model also includes the micromechanics behaviour, which comes from a micromechanics reference model.

The implementation of this model into a commercial code gives rise to two major difficulties. The first is related to the nonlocal character of the model which results from i) the damage indicator being uniform throughout the thickness of the elementary layer and ii) the layer-interface coupling. The second difficulty is that the model is defined in the scale of the elementary layer and, therefore, if one really wants to use to simulate an industrial structure one must expect a large number of DOFs.

In order to deal with these difficulties, we chose to write our own finite element software (Coffee) [11]. The main advantage of this approach is that we are not constrained by the architecture of an existing code. Our program is written in an object-oriented language (C++), which result in a very modular code. *Classes* were designed in such a way that the introduction of new functions, behaviour laws or element types has very little impact on the rest of the code. Thus, new capabilities (*i.e.* specific solvers or pre-processing procedure) can be added very easily.

The resolution algorithm implemented is a classical and very robust step-by-step algorithm in which at each step the system of nonlinear equation is solved through Newton-Raphson iterations.

A parallel linear solver is used to calculate the global equilibrium in the Newton-Raphson scheme. This parallel solver uses a Domain Decomposition Method (DDM) for the parallelization.

Illustrations

In this section, we illustrate the level of performance, which can be expected from the mesomodel.

Figure 3 shows the dimensions of a $[0/90]_s$ T700-M21 composite plate and the response in traction. A defect was introduced into the 0° layer to ensure the localisation of fracture in the middle of the specimen.

Figure 3 Composite plate (left) and behaviour in traction (right).

Figure 4 shows the fibre breakage damage indicator (d_f) just before failure. The maximal level of loading that the plate can hold defines failure point. After failure the fracture propagates very quickly crossing the entire specimen.

Figure 4 Fibre breakage damage indicator (d_f) for the 0° layer; Just before failure (left) and at the end of the simulation (right).

The second case is a Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimen. The delamination specimen used in this example is shown in Figure 5. Its parameters are: $a = 20$ mm; $B = 20$ mm; $l = 200$ mm; $h = 2$ mm.

Figure 5 The delamination specimen

We are interested in the comparison of the numerical results obtained using our technique with the experimental results given in [11]. In [11], three T300 Vicotex M10 carbon-epoxy DCB specimens were tested. For the simulation, we chose a unidirectional-type specimen ($0^\circ/0^\circ$). In the discretization process, special care was taken to ensure good representation of the interlaminar stresses at the crack's tip. In this case only the interface is damageable. Figure 6 shows the load applied to one arm of the specimen vs. the vertical displacement of the point of application. Figure 6 also shows

some experimental results from [11] and results of a simulation using a beam model from [12].

Figure 6 Comparison between experiment and simulation
(force vs. displacement)

The comparison shows good agreement between these experimental and numerical results.

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